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ATTITUDE TOWARDS MATHEMATICS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the attitude towards Mathematics in relation to academic performance of Grade 11 students of Liceo De La Salle – Senior High School during the first quarter of school year 2018-2019. Descriptive-correlational research design employing the survey method was used. Three hundred thirteen students of Liceo De La Salle were the target participants. The Attitude Towards Mathematics Inventory (ATMI) by Tapia and Marsh (2004) was used to determine their level of attitude towards Mathematics, while their first quarter grades in General Mathematics were secured to determine their academic performance. Data gathered were tabulated and analyzed using Chi-square test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Results revealed that the students' attitude towards Mathematics when taken as a whole was neutral ($m=3.40$). Students from the STEM strand have positive attitude towards Mathematics ($m=3.57$). Likewise, male students have positive attitude towards Mathematics ($m=3.53$). Their academic performance in Mathematics as a whole was very satisfactory ($m=86.25$). STEM students' academic performance was outstanding ($m=90.27$), ABM and HUMSS students obtained satisfactory mean scores ($m=83.28$; $m=82.72$), while TVL and HUMSS revealed fairly satisfactory mean scores ($m=79.82$; $m=79.00$). There is a significant relationship between the level of attitude towards Mathematics and their chosen strand. Furthermore, there exists a significant relationship between their attitude towards Mathematics and their academic performance in Mathematics. Lastly, there is a significant difference between their academic performance and their chosen strand.

Keywords: Attitudes towards Mathematics, Academic Performance, Mathematics Education, Senior High School, Grade 11, ATMI

INTRODUCTION

Today's modern world where change is accelerating and where there is a need for Mathematics as a way of representing, communicating, and predicting events is ever increasing. It can be argued that the need to understand and be able to utilize Mathematics in daily life and in the workplace becomes important requirements in the 21st century. The principles of Mathematics appear in many ways in daily life: the world of finance, insurance issues, social decisions based on Statistics and Probability, engineering, medicine, as well as the routine use of number and shape (Alenezi, 2008).

Mathematics is the study of the relations between objects or quantities. It is defined in the Cambridge Dictionary (2003) as "the study of numbers, shapes and space using reason and usually a special system of symbols and rules for organizing them." It can be debated that this definition is just an external description of Mathematics and that Mathematics is more inclusive and universal than this description. Steen (1990) defines Mathematics as "an exploratory science that seeks to understand every kind of pattern. Patterns that occur in nature, patterns invented by human mind, and even patterns created by other patterns."

In the Philippines, it is not new that Filipino students see Mathematics as a difficult subject in school. Results of National Achievement Tests (NAT) for several years support these findings that Filipino students are poor in Mathematics. In the 1999 and 2003 results of Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), the Philippines ranked third and fourth from the bottom of the participating countries in terms of Mathematics achievement. But recently, the Philippine team won third place at the International Regions Mathematics League (IRML) in Las Vegas in early June of 2018. The Philippine team, composed of 22 students from different high schools across the country, competed in the event held on June 1-2 at the University of Nevada, Las Vegas. In this competition, China and Macau ranked first and second, respectively. The Philippines' final score was one point higher than that of South Korea, which

placed 4th. This shows that the Filipinos are improving in the field of Mathematics (Baizas, 2018).

Learners as social beings with personal beliefs, emotions and views, and most especially, students' attitudes should be considered in the learning process. Their motivation to learn plays an important role for their academic achievement. Thus, attitude cannot be easily separated from learning because the former is acquired through the process of learning (Akinsola & Olowojaiye, 2008).

This study was motivated by the curiosity of most teachers including the researcher's on why students, more often than not, have a dislike for Mathematics. That is why, the researcher wanted to relate students' attitude in Mathematics to their academic performance. A great deal of research on students' attitudes towards Mathematics has centered on Western samples, while few studies have been conducted in Asia. This limits teachers' understanding of their attitude towards Mathematics when related to their academic performance worldwide. In addition, this study is also one of the first to use the Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI) by Tapia and Marsh (2004) which has four distinct factors, namely: enjoyment, self-concept, motivation, and value of Mathematics.

METHODS

Research Design

Descriptive-correlational research design employing the survey method was used in this study. This research design was considered appropriate because it is concerned with the present phenomena in terms of conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, relationships, or trends invariably (Aggarwal, 1998, as cited in Salaria, 2012; Kowalczyk, 2015). Moreover, this study sought to find out students' attitude towards Mathematics and its relation to their academic performance, a situation existing at the time of the study.

Participants

A total of 313 Grade 11 students from all the strands of Liceo De La Salle Senior High School of the University of St. La Salle, Bacolod City, Negros Occidental were involved in the study. A multi-stage sampling method was used in selecting the participants, making use of the stratified random sampling using proportionate selection first, to categorize them according to their chosen strands, which was done per strand. Then, cluster sampling through lottery was used to identify what sections to take as samples, which was also done per strand. All students from the drawn sections were taken except for the last section drawn, which was chosen by lottery to preserve the randomness of data and to complete the sample size.

Instrument

The research instrument consisted of two parts. Part One sought to gather students' personal information including name, sex, type of school graduated from high school, and their chosen strand in senior high school. Part Two aimed to determine their level of attitude towards Mathematics, using a standardized questionnaire by Tapia and Marsh (2004) known as Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI). The instrument was composed of 40 items divided into four factors patterned after Tapia and Marsh (2004), which are enjoyment, self-concept, motivation, and value. Using a five-point Likert scale, each description was assigned according to positive or negative ideas.

Scale	Numerical Value for Positive Statements	Numerical Value for Negative Statements	Description
E	5	1	Fully accepts and believes that the statement is true
D	4	2	Accept that the statement is true
C	3	3	Partly believes that the statement is true
B	2	4	Denies that the statement is true
A	1	5	Fully denies that the statement is true

Descriptive interpretations of the mean scores indicate the levels of attitude towards Mathematics, distributed as follows:

Mean Score Range	Verbal Interpretation	Description
4.21 – 5.00	Very Positive	Has a strong positive attitude towards mathematics
3.41 – 4.20	Positive	Has a positive attitude towards mathematics
2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Has an impartial attitude towards mathematics
1.81 – 2.60	Negative	Has a negative attitude towards mathematics
1.00 – 1.80	Very Negative	Has a strong negative attitude towards mathematics

Table 1

Items in the Four Factors of the Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI)

ATMI Factors	Positive Items	Negative Items	Frequency	
			Positive Items	Negative Items
Enjoyment	3, 24, 26, 27, 29, 30, 31, 37, 38	25	9	1
Self-concept	16, 17, 18, 19, 22, 40	9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 20, 21	6	9
Motivation	23, 32, 33, 34	28	4	1
Value	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 35, 36, 39		10	
TOTAL			29	11

The Mathematics subject being offered during the time of the study was General Mathematics during the first semester of the school year from which the students' grades were taken to measure their academic performance. Grades were distributed and interpreted using the mean range based on the USLS-IS handbook, as shown below:

Scale	Interpretation	Description
90-100	Outstanding	A student complied with the maximum requirements in all fields of study.
85-89	Very Satisfactory	A student complied very adequately with the requirements in all fields of study.
80-84	Satisfactory	A student complied with fairly more than the minimum requirements in all fields of study.
75-59	Fairly Satisfactory	A student complied with the minimum requirements in all fields of study.
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	A student has not complied with the minimum requirements in all fields of study.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The validity of the Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory has been established for high school students (Tapia & Marsh, 2004).

The Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory has high internal reliability with Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.963 (Tapia & Marsh, 2004). After factor analysis was conducted on the data, four factors were retained. The four remaining factors were Self-concept (15 items), Value of Mathematics (10 items), Enjoyment (10 items), and Motivation (5 items). The 40-item inventory was estimated to take between 10 and 20 minutes to complete (Tapia & Marsh, 2004).

Data Treatment

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data: mean, Chi-square, ANOVA, and z-test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Attitude of Grade 11 Students Towards Mathematics

When Grouped According to Strand

Table 2 shows that students from the STEM strand obtained a positive level of attitude towards Mathematics (3.57), while the level of attitude towards Mathematics of those from ABM, HUMSS, TVL, and ARTS & DESIGN strands was neutral with mean scores (3.29, 3.17, 3.22, 3.38).

Table 2

Level of Attitude Towards Mathematics When Grouped According to Strand

Strand	Mean	Interpretation
STEM	3.57	Positive
ABM	3.29	Neutral
HUMSS	3.17	Neutral
TVL	3.22	Neutral
ARTS&DESIGN	3.38	Neutral

Since the STEM strand deals with higher level of Mathematics such as Pre-Calculus and Basic Calculus and that some of the STEM students will become engineers in the future, data implies that their attitude towards Mathematics should be positive. While the other strands will not use any rigorous or higher Mathematics in their line of work, then their attitude towards Mathematics is neutral. The result of the study conforms with that of Martinez and Fuller (1999) whereby career preferences pertain to the identification of one's work activities in relation to the individual's abilities, skills, and competencies for one to take greater job and personal responsibility for the future.

When Grouped According to Sex

Table 3 reveals that the level of attitude towards Mathematics among male students is positive (3.53), while the female students have a neutral attitude (3.32). This implies that male students have

a higher mean value in regard to their attitude towards Mathematics than that of the female students. This is likely due to the fact that most male students will pursue careers related to Mathematics, such as engineering. This result supports the study of Ernest (1996) in which Mathematics is perceived to be difficult, cold, abstract, and, most importantly, largely masculine. In addition, this conforms with the study of Stipek and Granlinski (1991), indicating that girls have lower expectations for themselves in Mathematics than boys, and that girls believe they do not have Mathematical ability. When girls do poorly in Mathematics, they attribute their poor performance to their inability to do Mathematics. Moreover, in the study of Mahanta and Islam (2016), it was concluded that boys show more positive attitude towards Mathematics than girls do. However, results of the present study are in contrast with those of Mohd et al. (2011), Köğçe et al. (2009), and Nicolaidou and Philippou (2003), which suggest that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards Mathematics between male and female students.

Table 3

Level of Attitude Towards Mathematics When Grouped According to Sex

Sex	Mean	Interpretation
Male	3.53	Positive
Female	3.32	Neutral

When Grouped According to the Type of School Graduated from Junior High School

Table 4 reveals that the level of attitude towards Mathematics of students who graduated from public junior high schools is positive (3.43), while the level of attitude towards Mathematics of students who graduated from private junior high schools is neutral (3.38). Result implies that students from public schools are more inclined in Mathematics than students from the private schools. This suggests that students from public schools have the capacity to obtain scholarship grants and to continue their senior high school at Liceo De La Salle. Most students at Liceo De La Salle from public schools are top performing students. Such finding conforms

with the study of Utsumi and Mendes (2000) in that students from government schools showed significantly high positive attitudes towards Mathematics as compared to students from private schools. This, however, contradicts the study of Miller and Moore (1991) who found that private school students showed significantly high positive attitudes towards Mathematics as compared to government school students.

Table 4

Level of Attitude Towards Mathematics When Grouped According to the Type of Graduated from Junior High School

Type of school graduated from Junior High School	Mean	Interpretation
Public	3.43	Positive
Private	3.38	Neutral

When Taken as a Whole and in Terms of the Factors of the Attitude Towards Mathematics Inventory

Table 5 reveals that out of the four factors of ATMI, *Value* has the highest mean score (3.98) interpreted as positive, while *Enjoyment*, *Self-Concept*, and *Motivation* factors have mean scores (3.32, 3.00, and 3.00, respectively), all interpreted as neutral. When taken as a whole, the mean of the level of attitude towards Mathematics is 3.40, which is interpreted as neutral. This implies that Grade 11 students believe that Mathematics is an important subject and that they all need Mathematics in their lives, thus the value factor got the highest mean score. However, they do not enjoy doing Mathematics, they do not possess the perception that they have the competence to do Mathematics, and they do not have the motivation to do Mathematics. The result also conforms with the study of Ediger and Rao (as cited in Ediger, 2009) stating that each person believes that there is a need to be able to use Mathematics in everyday transactions, such as buying necessary goods, services, and groceries, as well as pay bills. Furthermore, this is similar to the

study of Henderson (1980) claiming that the majority of people feel powerless in the presence of Mathematical ideas, hence they do not have enjoyment and, most importantly, self-concept in Mathematics.

Table 5

Level of Attitude Towards Mathematics When Taken as a Whole and in Terms of the Factors of ATMI

Factors	Mean	Interpretation
Enjoyment	3.32	Neutral
Self-concept	3.00	Neutral
Motivation	3.00	Neutral
Value	3.98	Positive
As a whole	3.40	Neutral

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 11 Students in Mathematics When Grouped According to Strand

Table 6 reveals that the level of academic performance in Mathematics of the STEM strand has a mean of 90.27, interpreted as Outstanding; the ABM strand's level of academic performance has a mean of 83.28, interpreted as Satisfactory; the HUMSS strand's level has a mean of 82.72, interpreted as Satisfactory; the TVL strand has a mean of 79.82, interpreted as Fairly Satisfactory; the ARTS & DESIGN strand's level of academic performance has a mean of 79.00, interpreted as Fairly Satisfactory, and when taken as a whole, the Grade 11 students obtained a mean of 86.25, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This implies that the STEM strand has the highest academic achievement which is outstanding in Mathematics and this is reasonable since they will be pursuing careers that have something to do with Mathematics. Next are the ABM and HUMSS strands with satisfactory ratings since they belong to the academic strands and they will still pursue higher education, hence will need Mathematical concepts to be used in college, especially the ABM strand which will pursue business related courses and accountancy. The TVL and ARTS & DESIGN strands have both got a low academic performance which is fairly satisfactory since the focus

of TVL is cookery, which does not need higher Mathematics, while the ARTS & DESIGN strand focuses on the arts. The finding of the study conform with that of Heilbronner (2011), claiming that the greater number of the students is manifested to proceed to the STEM courses. This could be attributed to the quality, adequacy of preparation and, above all, scholastic experiences of students.

Table 6

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 11 Students in Mathematics When Grouped According to Strand

Strand	Mean	Interpretation
STEM	90.27	Outstanding
ABM	83.28	Satisfactory
HUMSS	82.72	Satisfactory
TVL	79.82	Fairly Satisfactory
ARTS & DESIGN	79.00	Fairly Satisfactory
As a whole	86.25	Very Satisfactory

When Grouped According to Sex

Table 7 reveals that the level of academic performance in Mathematics of the male students has a mean of 86.49, interpreted as Very Satisfactory, while the female students' level of academic performance in Mathematics has a mean of 86.10, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This implies that when Grade 11 students are grouped according to sex, the mean of their academic performance in Mathematics tends to gravitate around the very satisfactory mark. This result is in conformity with the study of Khatoon (1988) in that there is no significant difference in the Mathematical aptitude between boys and girls. In contrast to this, McGraw, Lubienski, and Strutchens (2006) claim that females are underrepresented in Mathematics and science-related careers because they tend to have low Mathematics achievement and participate less in advanced Mathematics courses.

Table 7

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 11 Students in Mathematics When Grouped According to Sex

Sex	Mean	Interpretation
Male	86.49	Very Satisfactory
Female	86.10	Very Satisfactory

When Grouped According to the Type of School Graduated from Junior High School

Table 8 shows that the level of academic performance in Mathematics of the students from the public junior high school has a mean of 87.24, interpreted as Very Satisfactory, while the level of academic performance in Mathematics of students from private junior high school has a mean of 85.61, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This implies that, at Liceo De La Salle Senior High School, students from public junior high schools are as competitive as students from private junior high schools. This can be attributed to the fact that students from public junior high schools are top performing students who got the scholarship grants to enroll in Liceo De La Salle. This study conforms to the study of study of Keeves (1978) in which the type of school, classified as public or private, did not make any difference in terms of students' academic performance.

Table 8

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 11 Students in Mathematics When Grouped According to the Type of School Graduated from Junior High School

Type of school graduated from Junior High School	Mean	Interpretation
Public	87.24	Very Satisfactory
Private	85.61	Very Satisfactory

Relationship Between Attitude Towards Mathematics of Grade 11 Students and Strands

Using 16 as degrees of freedom, the computed value is 30.49. Comparing the computed value from the tabular value of 26.30 shows that the computed value is higher or greater than the tabular value, which means that there is a significant relationship between the Grade 11 students' attitude towards Mathematics and their chosen strands. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Result reveals that the attitude towards Mathematics of Grade 11 students has a relation to their chosen strands in Senior High School. Positive attitude towards Mathematics would give a result that a student will likely choose a strand that is related to Mathematics like STEM and ABM rather than HUMSS, TVL, and ARTS & DESIGN. Results conform to the study of Owie (2003) in that the most important reason a student chooses a particular career is that the person has interest in the field, which in this case those who have positive attitude towards Mathematics tend to choose STEM and ABM strands. Results further agree to Ercikan, McCreith, and Lapointe (2005) in that students' attitudes toward Mathematics were the strongest predictor of their participation in advanced Mathematics courses.

Relationship of Attitude Towards Mathematics of Grade 11 Students and Sex

Using 4 as degrees of freedom, the computed value is 7.70. Comparing the computed value from the tabular value of 9.49 shows that the computed value is lower or less than the tabular, value which means that there is no significant relationship between the Grade 11 students' attitude towards Mathematics and their sex. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Result indicates that the attitude towards Mathematics of Grade 11 students has no relation to their sex. Whether one is a male or a female, it does not tell that one has a positive or a negative attitude towards Mathematics. Results are in conformity with the study of Farooq and Shah (2016) whereby male and female students of secondary schools have the same type of

attitude towards mathematics. This implies that gender differential has no impact on the attitude of students towards Mathematics. However, the results run counter to the studies of Boswell (1979), Fennema and Sherman (1977), Sherman (1882), Leder (1982), and Ethington (1992) in that at the secondary school level, most of the girls do not actively participate in Mathematics classes due to poor perceptions towards Mathematics.

Relationship of Attitude Towards Mathematics of Grade 11 Students and the Type of Junior High School They Graduated from

Using 4 as degrees of freedom, the computed value is 2.77. Comparing the computed value from the tabular value of 9.49 shows that the computed value is lower or less than the tabular value, which means that there is no significant relationship between the Grade 11 students' attitude towards Mathematics and the type junior high school graduated from. Hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Result reveals that the attitude towards Mathematics of Grade 11 students has no relation to the type of junior high school graduated from. Whether one graduated from a public high school or a private high school, it does not tell that one has a positive or a negative attitude towards Mathematics. Such results conform to the study of Abosalem (2015) in that there is no significant difference between students' attitudes toward Mathematics and students' high school type. This is in contrast to the study of Rosaly (1993) whereby the attitude of high school students towards Mathematics and their achievements in Mathematics are highly correlated.

Relationship of Attitude Towards Mathematics and Academic Performance in Mathematics of Grade 11 Students

Using 16 as degrees of freedom, the computed value is 54.35. Comparing the computed value from the tabular value of 26.30 shows that the computed value is higher or greater than the tabular value, which means that there is a significant relationship between the Grade 11 students' attitude towards Mathematics and their academic performance in Mathematics. Thus, the null hypothesis

is rejected. Result reveals that attitude towards Mathematics has a relationship with academic performance of Grade 11 students. Positive attitude towards Mathematics would result in positive academic performance in Mathematics. Such findings support the studies of Volet (1997), Middleton (1999), Christou (2001), Singh et al. (2002), and Hammouri (2004) in which favorable attitudes toward Mathematics lead to higher achievement in the subject. This also conforms to the study of Costello (1991), noting that positive attitudes toward Mathematics lead to greater effort and in turn to higher achievement. The study of Neale, Gill, and Tismer (1970) further confirm on the results of their study that there is a significant correlation between attitude and achievement in Mathematics. Furthermore, the study of Christou (2001) states that achievement in Mathematics helps to develop attitudes toward Mathematics. However, results are in contrast with the study of Cresswell and Gubb (1987), claiming that none of this work has been able to resolve the problem whether positive attitudes towards a particular area of study enable students to succeed in that area or whether success in a subject breeds positive attitudes.

Difference Between Level of Academic Performance in Mathematics When Grouped According to Strand

The computed value of the ANOVA F-test is 23.10. Comparing the computed value from the tabular value of 2.40 shows that the computed value is higher or greater than the tabular value, which means that there is a significant difference between the Grade 11 students' academic performance in Mathematics and their chosen strands. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. When the Scheffe's test was done, result shows that there is significant difference in the academic performance in Mathematics when STEM strand is compared to the other strands, namely: ABM, HUMSS, TVL, and ARTS & DESIGN. However, if one compares ABM and HUMSS, ABM and TVL, ABM and ARTS & DESIGN, HUMSS and TVL, HUMSS and ARTS & DESIGN, and TVL and ARTS & DESIGN, except comparing STEM to other strands, no significant difference can be found. The STEM strand has higher academic performance

than ABM, HUMSS, TVL, and ARTS & DESIGN; the ABM strand has higher academic performance than HUMSS, TVL and ARTS & DESIGN; the HUMSS strand has higher academic performance than TVL and ARTS & DESIGN; and the TVL strand has a higher academic performance than ARTS & DESIGN. Such result reveals that the academic performance in Mathematics of Grade 11 students has a significant difference in terms of their chosen strands. Most students enrolled in the STEM strand have higher academic performance in Mathematics than the students enrolled in other strands. Furthermore, the result shows that there is a significant difference in the academic performance in Mathematics if and only if one compares the STEM strand to the other strands. This denotes that the STEM students are very well-versed in the Mathematics subject. Furthermore, results conform to the study of La (2009) indicating that factors influencing the educational and career choices of senior high school students include parents' support, school structure, gender and, most importantly, grade point average. Moreover, the result is in conformity with the study of Heilbronner (2011) claiming that the greater number of the students is manifested to proceed to the STEM courses. This is due to the quality, adequacy of preparations and, above all, scholastic experiences of the students.

Difference Between Level of Academic Performance in Mathematics When Grouped According to Sex

The computed value of the z-test is 0.4105. Comparing the computed value from the tabular value of 1.96 shows that the computed value is lower or less than the tabular value, which means that there is no significant difference between the Grade 11 students' academic performance in Mathematics and their sex. So, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Result of this study reveals that the academic performance in Mathematics of Grade 11 students has no significant difference in terms of sex. Thus, it is not true that if one is a male, then one is better in Mathematics than the female. This is in conformity with the study of Khatoon (1988) who found no significant difference in the aptitude for Mathematics among boys and girls. However, this is in contrast to the study of Larouche (2000)

in which girls were less successful than boys in Mathematics. Result is likewise in contrast to the study of Hanna (2000) noting that sex difference in Mathematics and Science achievement persists.

Difference Between Level of Academic Performance in Mathematics When Grouped According to the Type of Junior High School Graduated from

The computed value of the z-test is 1.7317. Comparing the computed value from the tabular value of 1.96 shows that the computed value is lower or less than the tabular value, which means that there is a no significant difference between the Grade 11 students' academic performance in Mathematics and the type of junior high school graduated from. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Result denotes that the academic performance in Mathematics of Grade 11 students has no significant difference in the type of junior high school graduated from. It does not mean that if one is from a private junior high school, then one is better in Mathematics than the students from public junior high schools. This supports the study of Keeves (1978) stating that the type of school, classified as public or private, did not make any difference upon students' academic performance. However, such findings run counter to the study of Ajayi (2006) and Philiias and Wanjobi (2011), claiming that school type, either private or public, has an effect on the academic performance of students in Mathematics.

CONCLUSION

When it comes to the level of attitude towards Mathematics, STEM students showed positive attitudes towards Mathematics since they will pursue degrees and courses utilizing advanced Mathematics. Male students exhibit a higher mean value of attitude towards Mathematics than female students do since most males will pursue careers that are closely related to Mathematics, such as engineering. Students from public junior high schools have a

positive attitude towards Mathematics because most of them are top performing students from different public junior high schools.

Grade 11 students know the value of Mathematics, of how it could be used in everyday life and of how it could be of help in their future jobs. They understand that Mathematics is a very important subject, but they do not have the enjoyment to do Mathematics, they do not have the perception that they have the competence to do Mathematics, and they do not have the motivation to start learning and enjoying it.

In terms of the level of academic performance in Mathematics, STEM students will be the future engineers, scientists, statisticians, and mathematicians since they possess outstanding performance in the Mathematics subject. ABM and HUMSS strands still will need Mathematics in their college education. TVL and ARTS & DESIGN strands will not use any rigorous Mathematics when they reach the field and this is evident because they only have a fairly satisfactory performance in Mathematics. The student's performance in Mathematics does not have any bearing whether one is a male or a female. Likewise, the student's performance in Mathematics does not have any bearing whether a student came from a public junior high school or a private junior high school.

When a student's attitude towards Mathematics is positive, s/he tends to take up courses with Mathematics; therefore, one will take the STEM strand while in senior high school. Most of the students with positive attitude towards Mathematics can be found in the STEM strand. However, it does not follow that if a student's attitude towards Mathematics is positive, then s/he is a male and he/she is from a private junior high school. Moreover, when a Grade 11 student has a positive attitude towards Mathematics, s/he tends to have high performance in Mathematics. This is due to the fact one sees it as a fun and enjoyable subject and one is motivated to do it. However, students with negative attitude towards Mathematics tend to obtain low performance in Mathematics.

Grade 11 students' performance in Mathematics differs according to the strands they are in. STEM students would likely have higher academic performance in Mathematics than students in ABM, HUMSS, TVL, and ARTS & DESIGN strands. Sex does not show any difference in their academic performance in Mathematics, and neither does the type of junior high school one graduated from.

Findings of the study have generated the following recommendations. Mathematics teachers should try to reiterate that Mathematics is not only for the engineers or mathematicians. Mathematics exists in every discipline. Therefore, teachers should encourage their students about the beauty of Mathematics in arts and to the other disciplines as well. Also, the myth that boys are better than girls in Math should be emphasized that it is only a myth to restore the attitude towards Mathematics of female students. Finally, more scholarship grants should be given, if possible, to attract even more top performing students from public junior high schools who cannot afford the tuition fees of private schools.

Furthermore, the challenge for teachers is to inspire students for them to enjoy Mathematics, acquire self-concept, and have the motivation to do Mathematics. They should find better ways, innovative strategies, and creative techniques, thus improving their practices in the teaching of Mathematics to heighten students' attitudes towards Mathematics and, in turn, improve their academic performance in the subject.

A training program may be developed by the Mathematics department for non-STEM students that will present ways to improve Mathematics skills so that their academic performance in the subject area will improve.

Students' attitude towards Mathematics has something to do with their chosen strands. Guidance counsellors may give a talk or conduct a forum with representatives of different strands to discuss varying attitudes towards Mathematics so that proper intervention will be implemented. Likewise, attitude towards Mathematics has something to do with students' academic performance in

Mathematics. As previously mentioned, intervention should be that the Mathematics department will conduct training programs and the guidance office will give a talk or a forum. They should work hand-in-hand so that whatever results the guidance office can gather, such must serve as feedback to the Mathematics department so that teachers will know how they can penetrate through the minds of students and hopefully help them in their difficulties in Mathematics, especially to the non-STEM strands.

Academic performance in Mathematics has something to do with their chosen strands. Mathematics teachers must give enough time, patience, and consideration to students in non-STEM sections since their Mathematics abilities are not that high compared to STEM students. When giving examples and exercises, teachers try to make sure that the examples are suited to their chosen strands so that they can relate to the topic.

For future researchers, similar studies may be conducted to Grade 11 students of other senior high schools to have a more comprehensive result and to validate the findings of the study.

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